

A REFINEMENT OF A PARTITION THEOREM OF SELLERS

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Abstract

Abel's identity

$$a_1b_1 + a_2b_2 + \cdots + a_mb_m = (b_1 + b_2 + \cdots + b_m)a_m + (b_1 + \cdots + b_{m-1})(a_{m-1} - a_m) + \cdots + b_1(a_1 - a_2)$$

is used to give a refinement of a recent theorem of Sellers.

1. Introduction

Recently Sellers ([1], [2]) proved via partition analysis the following theorem.

Theorem 1. Let $K = (k_2, k_3, k_4, \dots)$ be an infinite vector of nonnegative integers with $k_2 \geq 1$. Define $p(n; K)$ as the number of partitions of n of the form $p_1 + p_2 + p_3 + p_4 + \cdots$ with $p_1 \geq p_2 \geq p_3 \geq p_4 \cdots \geq 0$ and $p_1 \geq k_2p_2 + k_3p_3 + k_4p_4 + \cdots$. Then, for all $n \geq 0$, $p(n; K)$ equals the number of partitions of n whose parts must be 1's or of the form $(\sum_{i=2}^m k_i) + (m - 1)$ for some integer $m \geq 2$.

The main result of this note is a refinement of Sellers's theorem. To state the theorem, we will first introduce some notation.

Definition 1. Let j be a nonnegative integer and let $K = (k_2, k_3, k_4, \dots)$ be a sequence of nonnegative integers with $k_2 \geq 1$.

Define

- (1) $K_1 := \emptyset$ and $K_m := (k_2, k_3, \dots, k_m)$ for $m \geq 2$.
- (2) $S_j(n; K_1) :=$ the set of all partitions of n with exactly the part j ,
and for $m \geq 2$

$S_j(n; K_m) :=$ the set of all partitions of n with $n = p_1 + p_2 + \cdots + p_m$,
 $p_1 \geq p_2 \geq \cdots \geq p_m \geq 1$, and $p_1 = j + k_2p_2 + k_3p_3 + \cdots + k_mp_m$.

(3) $T_j(n; K_1) :=$ the set of all partitions of n with 1 appearing exactly j times and with
 largest part ≤ 1 ,
 and for $m \geq 2$

$T_j(n; K_m) :=$ the set of all partitions in which the only parts appearing are $1, k_2 + 1,$
 $k_2 + k_3 + 2, \cdots, k_2 + k_3 + \cdots + k_m + m - 1$, the largest part equals
 $k_2 + k_3 + \cdots + k_m + m - 1$, and 1 appears exactly j times.

(4) $S(n; K_m) := \bigcup_{j \geq 0} S_j(n; K_m),$
 $T(n; K_m) := \bigcup_{j \geq 0} T_j(n; K_m),$
 $S(n; K) := \bigcup_{m \geq 1} T(n; K_m),$
 $T(n; K) := \bigcup_{m \geq 1} T(n; K_m).$

(5) We will use the following notation for a partition $p_1f_1 + p_2f_2 + \cdots + p_mf_m$ of n :

$$n = p_1 \cdot (f_1) + p_2 \cdot (f_2) + \cdots + p_m \cdot (f_m),$$

where f_i denotes the multiplicity of the part p_i and $p_1 \geq p_2 \geq \cdots \geq p_m$.

With the notation in Definition 1, we can now state our main result:

Theorem 2. We have

$$|S_j(n; K_m)| = |T_j(n; K_m)|,$$

for integers $j, n \geq 0$ and $m \geq 1$.

Remark. Sellers's Theorem 1 says that

$$\sum_{j \geq 0} \sum_{m \geq 1} |S_j(n; K_m)| = \sum_{j \geq 0} \sum_{m \geq 1} |T_j(n; K_m)|,$$

and this follows immediately from Theorem 2.

In Section 2, Abel's transform will be defined. In Section 3, Abel's transform will be used to give a short proof of the main result. In Section 4, two examples will be given.

2. Abel’s Identity, Abel’s Transform, and the Conjugation of Partitions

Abel’s identity states that, for $a_i, b_i \in \mathbb{R}$, one has

$$a_1b_1 + a_2b_2 + \cdots + a_mb_m = (b_1 + b_2 + \cdots + b_m)a_m + (b_1 + b_2 + \cdots + b_{m-1})(a_{m-1} - a_m) \tag{1}$$

$$+ \cdots + b_1(a_1 - a_2),$$

which can be readily verified by induction.

Let $p_1 \cdot (f_1) + p_2 \cdot (f_2) + \cdots + p_m \cdot (f_m)$ be a partition of n .

Define Abel’s transform α by

$$\alpha : p_1 \cdot (f_1) + p_2 \cdot (f_2) + \cdots + p_m \cdot (f_m) \rightarrow (f_1 + f_2 + \cdots + f_m) \cdot (p_m) \tag{2}$$

$$+ (f_1 + f_2 + \cdots + f_{m-1}) \cdot (p_{m-1} - p_m)$$

$$+ \cdots + f_1 \cdot (p_1 - p_2)$$

It follows from (1) that α^2 is the identity map. Hence α is a bijection. Indeed, α is the conjugation of partitions. This bijection, together with other two, will provide a bijection between the two sets $S_j(n; k_m)$ and $T_j(n; k_m)$ in the next section.

3. Proof of Theorem 2

By use of Abel’s transform α , we are in a position to prove Theorem 2.

Proof of Theorem 2. Let $n = p_1 + p_2 + \cdots + p_m$ be a partition in $S_j(n; k_m)$. Write $n = j + p_2 \cdot (k_2 + 1) + p_3 \cdot (k_3 + 1) + \cdots + p_m \cdot (k_m + 1)$. Combining the sequence of bijections

$$n = j + p_2 \cdot (k_2 + 1) + p_3 \cdot (k_3 + 1) + \cdots + p_m \cdot (k_m + 1)$$

$$\rightarrow n - j = p_2 \cdot (k_2 + 1) + p_3 \cdot (k_3 + 1) + \cdots + p_m \cdot (k_m + 1)$$

$$\xrightarrow{\alpha} n - j = (k_2 + k_3 + \cdots + k_m + (m - 1)) \cdot p_m + (k_2 + k_3 + \cdots + k_{m-1} + (m - 2)) \cdot$$

$$(p_{m-1} - p_m) + \cdots + (k_2 + 1) \cdot (p_2 - p_3)$$

$$\rightarrow n = (k_2 + k_3 + \cdots + k_m + (m - 1)) \cdot p_m + (k_2 + k_3 + \cdots + k_{m-1} + (m - 2)) \cdot$$

$$(p_{m-1} - p_m) + \cdots + (k_2 + 1) \cdot (p_2 - p_3) + 1 \cdot (j),$$

we see that the last partition is in $T_j(n; k_m)$. Hence $|S_j(n; k_m)| = |T_j(n; k_m)|$. □

4. Examples

Example 1. The case $K = (2, 1, 1, 1, \dots)$ and $n = 12$.

In this case, we have $(k_2 + 1, k_2 + k_3 + 2, k_2 + k_3 + k_4 + 3, \dots) = (3, 5, 7, 9, 11, \dots)$,

$$S(12; K) = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} 12 \\ 11 + 1, 10 + 2, 9 + 3, 8 + 4 \\ 10 + 1 + 1, 9 + 2 + 1, 8 + 3 + 1, 8 + 2 + 2 \\ 9 + 1 \cdot (3), 8 + 2 + 1 + 1, 7 + 2 + 2 + 1 \\ 8 + 1 \cdot (4), 7 + 2 + 1 \cdot (3) \\ 7 + 1 \cdot (5) \end{array} \right\},$$

and

$$T(12; K) = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} 1 \cdot (12) \\ 3 + 1 \cdot (9), 3 + 3 + 1 \cdot (6), 3 \cdot (3) + 1 \cdot (3), 3 \cdot (4) \\ 5 + 1 \cdot (7), 5 + 3 + 1 \cdot (4), 5 + 3 + 3 + 1, 5 + 5 + 1 + 1 \\ 7 + 1 \cdot (5), 7 + 5, 7 + 3 + 1 + 1 \\ 9 + 1 \cdot (3), 9 + 3 \\ 11 + 1 \end{array} \right\}.$$

We have the following partition of $S(12; K)$ and $T(12; K)$ into corresponding subsets.

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} S(12; K_1) = \{12\}, \\ T(12; K_1) = \{1 \cdot (12)\}, \\ S(12; K_2) = \{11 + 1, 10 + 2, 9 + 3, 8 + 4\}, \\ T(12; K_2) = \{3 + 1 \cdot (9), 3 + 3 + 1 \cdot (6), 3 \cdot (3) + 1 \cdot (3), 3 \cdot (4)\}, \\ S(12; K_3) = \{10 + 1 + 1, 9 + 2 + 1, 8 + 3 + 1, 8 + 2 + 2\}, \\ T(12; K_3) = \{5 + 1 \cdot (7), 5 + 3 + 1 \cdot (4), 5 + 3 + 3 + 1, 5 + 5 + 1 + 1\}, \\ S(12; K_4) = \{9 + 1 \cdot (3), 8 + 2 + 1 + 1, 7 + 2 + 2 + 1\}, \\ T(12; K_4) = \{7 + 1 \cdot (5), 7 + 5, 7 + 3 + 1 + 1\}, \\ S(12; K_5) = \{8 + 1 \cdot (4), 7 + 2 + 1 \cdot (3)\}, \\ T(12; K_5) = \{9 + 1 \cdot (3), 9 + 3\}, \\ S(12; K_6) = \{7 + 1 \cdot (5)\}, \\ T(12; K_6) = \{11 + 1\}. \end{array} \right.$$

We further partition these subsets. For example, in $S(12; K_3)$ and $T(12; K_3)$ we have

$$\begin{aligned} S_7(12; K_3) &= \{10 + 1 + 1\}, & T_7(12; K_3) &= \{5 + 1 \cdot (7)\}, \\ S_4(12; K_3) &= \{9 + 2 + 1\}, & T_4(12; K_3) &= \{5 + 3 + 1 \cdot (4)\}, \\ S_1(12; K_3) &= \{8 + 3 + 1\}, & T_1(12; K_3) &= \{5 + 3 + 3 + 1\}, \\ S_2(12; K_3) &= \{8 + 2 + 2\}, & T_2(12; K_3) &= \{5 + 5 + 1 + 1\}. \end{aligned}$$

and all other $S_j(12; K_3)$ and $T_j(12; K_3)$ are empty.

We demonstrate, for example, $|S_1(12; K_3)| = |T_1(12; K_3)|$. Take $12 = 8 + 3 + 1$, a partition

in $S_1(12; K_3)$. Since $8 = 1 + 3 \cdot (2) + 1 \cdot (1)$, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 12 = 8 + 3 + 1 = 8 + 3 \cdot (1) + 1 \cdot (1) = 1 + 3 \cdot (3) + 1 \cdot (2) &\rightarrow 11 = 3 \cdot (3) + 1 \cdot (2) \\
 &\xrightarrow{\alpha} 11 = (3 + 2) \cdot 1 + 3 \cdot (3 - 1) \\
 &= 5 \cdot (1) + 3 \cdot (2) \\
 &\rightarrow 12 = 5 \cdot (1) + 3 \cdot (2) + 1 \cdot (1) \\
 &= 5 + 3 + 3 + 1
 \end{aligned}$$

The corresponding Ferrers graph is

Example 2. The case $K = (1, 1, 1, \dots)$ and $n = 11$.
 In this case, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 (k_2 + 1, k_2 + k_3 + 2, k_2 + k_3 + k_4 + 3, \dots) &= (2, 4, 6, 8, \dots), \\
 S_3(11, K_3) &= \{7 + 3 + 1, 7 + 2 + 2\},
 \end{aligned}$$

and

$$T_3(11, K_3) = \{4 + 4 + 1 \cdot (3), 4 + 2 + 2 + 1 \cdot (3)\}.$$

We demonstrate $|S_3(11, K_3)| = |T_3(11, K_3)|$.

Since $7 = 3 + 3 \cdot (1) + 1 \cdot (1)$, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 11 = 7 + 3 + 1 = 7 + 3 \cdot (1) + 1 \cdot (1) &= 3 + 3 \cdot (2) + 1 \cdot (2) \\
 &\rightarrow 8 = 3 \cdot (2) + 1 \cdot (2) \\
 &\xrightarrow{\alpha} 8 = (2 + 2) \cdot 1 + 2 \cdot (3 - 1) \\
 &= 4 \cdot (1) + 2 \cdot (2) \\
 &\rightarrow 11 = 4 \cdot (1) + 2 \cdot (2) + 1 \cdot (3).
 \end{aligned}$$

The corresponding Ferrers graph is

Next, since $7 = 3 + 2 \cdot (1) + 2 \cdot (1)$, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 11 = 7 + 2 + 2 = 7 + 2 \cdot (1) + 2 \cdot (1) &= 3 + 2 \cdot (2) + 2 \cdot (2) \\
 &\rightarrow 8 = 2 \cdot (2) + 2 \cdot (2) \\
 &\xrightarrow{\alpha} 8 = (2 + 2) \cdot (2) + 2 \cdot (2 - 2) \\
 &= 4 \cdot (2) \\
 &\rightarrow 11 = 4 \cdot (2) + 1 \cdot (3).
 \end{aligned}$$

The corresponding Ferrers graph is

Therefore, $|S_3(11, K_3)| = |T_3(11, K_3)|$.

References

[1] J. A. Sellers, *Extending a recent result of Santos on partitions into odd parts*, INTEGERS: Electronic Journal of Combinatorial Number Theory 3 (2003), #A04.
 [2] J. A. Sellers, *Corrigendum to Article A4, Volume 3 (2003)*, INTEGERS 4 (2004), #A08.